

Intelligent UAV Path Planning for Ergodic Rate Maximization of MIMO Multipath Channels

Christian Vitale, Evangelos Vlachos, Panayiotis Kolios, and Georgios Ellinas

Abstract—Reliable communication between ground control stations and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is fundamental for safe, autonomous, and coordinated flight operations. This work presents a decentralized model predictive control (MPC) framework that jointly optimizes UAV trajectory planning and high-frequency MIMO communication performance, explicitly accounting for multipath channel effects. The proposed framework incorporates ergodic spectral efficiency, derived from realistic location-dependent channel modeling, into the control cost function, thereby enabling UAV trajectories to dynamically balance three key objectives: (i) minimize travel time to assigned targets, (ii) maintain probabilistic safety through minimum separation constraints under stochastic disturbances, and (iii) maximize the achievable uplink ergodic rate to the ground station. Simulation results confirm the effectiveness of the approach, showing that ergodic rate-aware path planning leads to improved trade-offs between communication quality, safety, and mission efficiency under practical channel conditions.

Index Terms—UAV path planning; mm-wave communications; MPC; ergodic rate; MIMO; collision avoidance; communication-aware control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, increasing attention has been devoted to the integrated design of control and communication strategies [1]–[8] to enable reliable, cooperative, and scalable autonomous UAV systems. Early works by Zeng et al. [1]–[3] laid the foundation for joint control-communication optimization, revealing the strong interdependence between mobility and wireless connectivity in autonomous vehicular systems. These studies introduced both theoretical frameworks and practical architectures for communication-aware navigation and platooning. More recent efforts have extended these ideas to UAV swarms, addressing challenges such as latency, interference, and spectral efficiency, particularly in the context of MIMO and millimeter-wave communication [4], [5]. These contributions highlight the intricate trade-offs between control accuracy and communication capacity under dynamic and distributed conditions. In parallel, Javaid et al. [6] surveyed the evolution of collaborative UAV communication systems, emphasizing reliability and the transition toward integrated

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communication–control paradigms. More recent advances by Girgis et al. [7] introduced the emerging field of semantic communication–control codesign, targeting efficiency, correlated dynamics, and mission-oriented performance. Finally, Li et al. [8] further explored MPC for UAV trajectory optimization under communication security constraints, demonstrating the potential of MPC for communication-aware autonomy.

Novelty and Scope: Despite recent progress, most existing approaches still rely on oversimplified wireless models, typically assuming line-of-sight (LOS) propagation and static channel conditions. Such assumptions neglect multipath fading, spatial channel variations, and the impact of external disturbances on both flight stability and communication performance, factors that are especially critical in cluttered or urban environments. Consequently, UAV trajectories may severely misestimate achievable data rates and link reliability, leading to suboptimal or even unsafe behaviors during coordinated missions. To overcome these limitations, this work proposes a decentralized MPC framework that explicitly integrates realistic, location-dependent multipath MIMO channel modeling into the control optimization process. Unlike conventional designs that treat communication quality as a static or independent constraint, the proposed framework incorporates ergodic spectral efficiency directly into the control cost function, while explicitly accounting for uncertainties that influence UAV motion. By integrating control, communication, and disturbance handling under multipath conditions, UAVs adapt their trajectories to the environment and other agents, maintaining connectivity and jointly maximizing throughput, safety, and robustness, beyond what LOS-based models can achieve.

Notation: \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{a} , and a denote matrices, vectors, and scalars, respectively. $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$, $|\cdot|$, $(\cdot)^\top$, $(\cdot)^*$, $\|\cdot\|$, and $\|\cdot\|_F$ denote the trace, absolute value, transpose, conjugate, Euclidean norm, and Frobenius norm, respectively. $(\mathbf{A})_{ij}$ is the (i, j) -th element of \mathbf{A} . $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes expectation; $\mathcal{N}(\alpha, \beta)$ and $\mathcal{CN}(\alpha, \beta)$ denote the real and complex Gaussian distributions with mean α and variance β , respectively. \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} denote the sets of real and complex numbers, respectively; $\mathbf{a}_{i:j}$ denotes the sequence of vectors \mathbf{a}_i to \mathbf{a}_j .

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Ergodic Rate for MIMO Multipath Channels

The uplink channel of a high-frequency $N \times N$ MIMO point-to-point communication system is considered, comprising a terrestrial base station (BS) located at a fixed position $\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} \triangleq [x_0, y_0, z_0]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in the common coordinate system, and a UAV at position $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Following a geometry-based stochastic channel model with L propagation paths, the channel gain between the i -th UAV transmit antenna and the j -th BS receive antenna is expressed as follows

$$(\mathbf{H})_{i,j} = \sum_{\ell=0}^{L-1} \alpha_{\ell} (\mathbf{A})_{i,j}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is defined as the outer product of the UAV's and BS steering vectors, with $|(\mathbf{A})_{i,j}| = 1$ for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N$. In this work, the focus is on the effect of multipath channel gains on UAV communication, and thus the steering-vector term is modeled as unity (wide-beam/omnidirectional operation). Incorporating analog/hybrid beam steering would amount to using a direction-dependent $A(\cdot)$ in Eq. (1) and is left for future work. Note that, at $f_c = 60$ GHz, the half-wavelength spacing is approximately 2.5 mm, making compact $N \times N$ arrays feasible on commercial UAV platforms. The complex gain of the ℓ -th UAV-BS path, α_{ℓ} , follows a Rician model:

$$\alpha_{\ell} = \begin{cases} \sigma_{\alpha_0}, & \ell = 0, \\ \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{\alpha_{\ell}}^2), & 1 \leq \ell \leq L-1, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

with

$$\sigma_{\alpha_{\ell}}^2 \triangleq P_{\text{TX}} \frac{\eta_{\text{eff}}}{L} \left(\frac{\lambda_c}{4\pi D_{\ell}} \right)^{\xi_{\ell}} e^{-D_{\ell} \mathcal{K}(f_c)}, \quad (3)$$

where P_{TX} is the UAV transmission power, η_{eff} is the antenna efficiency, λ_c is the carrier wavelength, and $\mathcal{K}(f_c)$ is the molecular absorption coefficient that depends on the carrier frequency f_c [9]. D_{ℓ} denotes the propagation distance between the BS and the UAV for the ℓ -th propagation path, whereas ξ_{ℓ} corresponds to the path loss exponent associated with that specific path. Note that, for the LOS path ($\ell = 0$), $D_0 = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} - \mathbf{p}\|$. For NLOS paths ($\ell > 0$), D_{ℓ} represents the total physical length of the corresponding indirect propagation route. For example, for a single-bounce reflected NLOS path,

$$D_{\ell} = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} - \mathbf{p}_{\ell}\| + \|\mathbf{p}_{\ell} - \mathbf{p}\|,$$

where \mathbf{p}_{ℓ} is the reflection point of path ℓ .

The *ergodic spectral efficiency* (or *ergodic rate*) of a MIMO multipath channel is defined as [10]

$$\bar{R} \triangleq \mathbb{E}[\log_2(1 + \text{SNR})] \quad (\text{bit/s/Hz}), \quad (4)$$

where the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is given by

$$\text{SNR} \triangleq \frac{\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2}{k_B K_{\text{abs}} B}, \quad (5)$$

with B , k_B , and K_{abs} denoting the bandwidth, Boltzmann's constant, and the absolute temperature, respectively.

To facilitate analytical treatment, the ergodic rate is approximated using a second-order Taylor expansion of $\log_2(1 + \text{SNR})$ around the mean SNR, $\mu = \mathbb{E}[\text{SNR}]$, followed by application of the expectation operator

$$\bar{R} \approx \log_2(1 + \mu) - \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \frac{\sigma^2}{(1 + \mu)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma^2 = \text{Var}(\text{SNR})$.

B. UAV System Model

This work considers a set \mathcal{M} of M UAVs operating autonomously within a shared airspace. The motion of each UAV $m \in \mathcal{M}$ follows a discrete-time linear dynamical model, as described in Eq. (7)

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \Phi \mathbf{x}_k + \Gamma \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{G} \mathbf{a}_k. \quad (7)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}_k = [\mathbf{p}_k, \boldsymbol{\nu}_k]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the UAV's state at time k , including its position $\mathbf{p}_k = [p_x, p_y, p_z]_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and velocity $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k = [\nu_x, \nu_y, \nu_z]_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in 3D Cartesian coordinates (with index m omitted for simplicity). The control input is the force vector applied by the UAV at time k , $\mathbf{u}_k = [u_x, u_y, u_z]_k^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The term $\mathbf{a}_k = [a_x, a_y, a_z]_k^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma)$ accounts for the impact of external disturbances (e.g., wind) and approximation errors, drawn from a zero-mean multivariate normal distribution with covariance Σ [11]. The system matrices Φ , Γ , and \mathbf{G} are defined as

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_3 & \delta T \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & \phi \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix}, \Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \gamma \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \delta T^2 \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \delta T \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where δT is the sampling interval, \mathbf{I}_3 and $\mathbf{0}_3$ are the 3×3 identity and zero matrices, respectively, ϕ models air resistance and $\gamma = \frac{\delta T}{\rho}$ depends on UAV mass ρ .

Assuming the disturbances \mathbf{a}_k are i.i.d. Gaussian, the UAV dynamics satisfy the Markov property. The state propagation over t steps can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+t} = \Phi^t \mathbf{x}_k + \sum_{n=0}^{t-1} \Phi^n (\Gamma \mathbf{u}_{k+t-n-1} + \mathbf{G} \mathbf{a}_{k+t-n-1}). \quad (9)$$

As the future disturbances are characterized only probabilistically rather than known exactly, Eq. (9) is used to compute the *predicted state distribution*. In particular, \mathbf{x}_{k+t} is Gaussian, i.e., $\mathbf{x}_{k+t} \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}, \Xi_{k+t})$, with mean and covariance

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t} &= \Phi^t \mathbf{x}_k + \sum_{n=0}^{t-1} \Phi^n \Gamma \mathbf{u}_{k+t-n-1}, \\ \Xi_{k+t} &= \sum_{n=0}^{t-1} \Phi^n \mathbf{Q} (\Phi^{\top})^n, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t} = [[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}, [\boldsymbol{\mu}_v]_{k+t}]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ contains the expected position $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and velocity $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_v]_{k+t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{G} \Sigma \mathbf{G}^{\top}$ is the covariance of the disturbances affecting the dynamics.

By selecting the control sequence $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+t-1}$ at time k , the UAV's future states are fully characterized stochastically (Eq. (10)). Notably, the prediction uncertainty is independent of the control inputs and can be pre-computed.

III. ROBUST UAV PATH PLANNING AND CHANNEL RATE MAXIMIZATION

This section presents the framework governing UAVs in the shared airspace. The approach integrates ergodic rate considerations directly into the cost function, enabling simultaneous optimization of UAV trajectories while accounting for the distinctive characteristics of MIMO multipath channel

propagation. The specific problem addressed in this work is formulated as follows:

Problem definition: For a group of UAVs denoted by \mathcal{M} , determine an optimal mobility strategy for each UAV m that balances three key goals: (i) arriving at its designated target $\mathbf{c}^m = (c_x^m, c_y^m, c_z^m) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in the shortest time feasible, (ii) ensuring safety by maintaining at least a minimum separation d_{MIN} from other UAVs or static obstacles with a probability of $1 - \epsilon$, and (iii) enhancing the experienced ergodic rate \bar{R} , as expressed in Eq. (4), towards a local ground station.

Using a distributed MPC approach [12], each UAV solves the problem sequentially at each time step applying the controls obtained via the following optimization

Communication MPC:

$$\min_{\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^m} \sum_{t=1}^T (w_D \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{c}^m\|^2] - w_C \bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)) \quad (11a)$$

subject to:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}^m \text{ as in Eq. (10)} \quad \forall t \quad (11b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}^i \text{ as in Eq. (10)} \quad \forall t, \forall i \quad (11c)$$

$$\|\mathbf{u}_{k+t}^m\| \leq \mathbf{u}_{\text{MAX}} \quad \forall t \quad (11d)$$

$$\|\mathbf{u}_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{u}_{k+t-1}^m\| \leq \Delta \mathbf{u} \quad \forall t \quad (11e)$$

$$\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}^m\| \leq \mathbf{v}_{\text{MAX}} \quad \forall t \quad (11f)$$

$$P(\|\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{p}_{k+t}^i\| \leq d_{\text{MIN}}) < \epsilon, \quad \forall t, \forall i \neq m \quad (11g)$$

where w_D and w_C are predefined weighting factors, $t \in [0, \dots, T-1]$, $i \in \mathcal{M}$, and $i \neq m$, represents any other UAV distinct from UAV m . Details of the distributed Communication MPC approach are provided in the following sections.

A. Analysis of the Control Cost Function and Constraints

For each t in the planning horizon T , the cost term guiding UAV m toward its target position \mathbf{c}^m is defined as the expected squared distance between its future position \mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m and \mathbf{c}^m

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{c}^m\|^2] = \text{Tr}([\boldsymbol{\Xi}_p]_{k+t}^m) + \|[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{c}^m\|^2, \quad (12)$$

where the equality follows from expanding the quadratic form and applying the identity $\mathbb{E}[(p_j^m)_{k+t}^2] = \text{Var}[(p_j^m)_{k+t}] + \mathbb{E}[(p_j^m)_{k+t}]^2$, with $j \in \{x, y, z\}$. Here, according to the predicted state distribution given in Eq. (10), $\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m \sim \mathcal{N}([\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^m, [\boldsymbol{\Xi}_p]_{k+t}^m)$, where $[\boldsymbol{\Xi}_p]_{k+t}^m \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the top-left block of the full state covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Xi}_{k+t}^m$, representing the position uncertainty of UAV m . Interestingly, this cost term depends deterministically on the control sequence $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^m$.

Eqs. (11b)–(11c) enforce the UAV dynamics, with Eq. (11b) relating the controls to UAV m 's state and Eq. (11c) predicting the expected positions of the other UAVs. To ensure realistic operation, Communication MPC constrains the applied controls and UAV speed as follows: (i) the control magnitude satisfies $\|\mathbf{u}_{k+t}^m\| \leq \mathbf{u}_{\text{MAX}}$ and consecutive inputs differ by at most $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ (Eqs. (11d)–(11e)); and (ii) the expected speed is bounded as $0 \leq \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}^m\| \leq \mathbf{v}_{\text{MAX}}$ (Eq. (11f)).

Eq. (11g) enforces UAV m 's safety by ensuring that the probability of inter-UAV distances falling below d_{MIN} remains below ϵ . Similar constraints can also be introduced to maintain a minimum distance from static obstacles. Being a stochastic

constraint, Eq. (11g) typically requires suitable approximations to enable tractable optimization. To this end, it is converted into an equivalent deterministic form. At each time $k+t$, 3D ellipsoids are defined around the expected positions of UAVs i and m , $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^i$ and $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^m$, such that each UAV remains inside its ellipsoid with probability $1 - \epsilon/2$, based on their Gaussian-distributed positions and covariances $[\boldsymbol{\Xi}_p]_{k+t}^i$, $[\boldsymbol{\Xi}_p]_{k+t}^m$ [13]. Ensuring that these ellipsoids are separated by at least d_{MIN} bounds the probability of violating the minimum distance. Specifically, UAVs may violate the constraint only if one leaves its ellipsoid. Consequently, a sufficient distance between the expected positions is imposed

$$d_{k+t}^{i,m} = r_{k+t}^i + r_{k+t}^m + d_{\text{MIN}}, \quad (13)$$

where r_{k+t}^i and r_{k+t}^m are the largest axes of the respective ellipsoids. This derivation ensures that

$$\|[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^m - [\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^i\| \geq d_{k+t}^{i,m} \implies P(\|\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m - \mathbf{p}_{k+t}^i\| \leq d_{\text{MIN}}) \leq 1 - (1 - \epsilon/2)^2 \leq \epsilon, \quad (14)$$

since the separation of the expected positions by at least $d_{k+t}^{i,m}$ ensures that a violation of the minimum distance d_{MIN} can occur only if at least one UAV lies outside its ellipsoidal uncertainty region.

As already mentioned, to solve the Communication MPC problem, a decentralized approach with a receding horizon of length T is employed, as in [12]. UAVs in \mathcal{M} follow a predefined sequence, with each UAV computing its trajectory at every time step under the assumption of perfect inter-UAV communication. At time step k , the first UAV in the sequence (UAV 1) determines its control inputs $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^1$ to plan its path over the horizon T , taking into account the previously established trajectories of UAVs 2 through M , and subsequently shares its plan with the others. In general, UAV m selects its control inputs $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^m$ by considering the latest trajectories of UAVs 1 to $m-1$ together with the previously computed plans of UAVs $m+1$ to M , before broadcasting its finalized route. In practice, delays or packet losses may cause planning based on outdated trajectories. However, the ellipsoidal safety buffers in Eq. (14) provide inherent robustness to such deviations, and a UAV can conservatively reuse the last received plan when an update is missed. A detailed analysis is left for future work.

Since $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^i$ is known at the time of optimization and $[\boldsymbol{\mu}_p]_{k+t}^m$ depends solely on UAV m 's control inputs, substituting Eq. (14) into Eq. (11g) and Eq. (12) into Eq. (11a) transforms the Communication MPC problem into a deterministic optimization, except for the ergodic rate computation, which is detailed in the following section. This deterministic problem can be efficiently solved using standard nonlinear optimization methods, such as interior point solvers. For a single UAV, the decision vector contains $3T$ control variables $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^m$. Since the box constraints in Eqs. (11d)–(11f) and the separation constraints in Eq. (11g) are enforced at each prediction step, the problem size grows linearly with the horizon length T and the number of UAVs M . In practice, the runtime is dominated by interior point iterations that compute a local solution. Each iteration solves a sparse linear system whose cost is polynomial in the problem dimension.

B. Analysis of the Ergodic Rate Cost Function

To integrate the ergodic rate $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$ into the Communication MPC optimization as a closed-form function of the control inputs $\mathbf{u}_{k:k+T-1}^m$, the second-order expansion presented in Eq. (6) is used. Specifically, the following is obtained:

$$\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m) \approx \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2]}{k_B K_{\text{abs}} B} \right) - \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \frac{\text{Var}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2]}{(k_B K_{\text{abs}} B)^2 \left(1 + \frac{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2]}{k_B K_{\text{abs}} B} \right)^2}. \quad (15)$$

Since the elements $(\mathbf{H})_{i,j}$ share identical statistics and are independent across (i, j) , the mean and variance of $\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2] &= N^2 \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{H})_{i,j} (\mathbf{H})_{i,j}^*], \\ \text{Var}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2] &= N^2 \text{Var}[(\mathbf{H})_{i,j} (\mathbf{H})_{i,j}^*]. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

From Eq. (2), each channel element is modeled as a complex Gaussian random variable

$$(\mathbf{H})_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\sigma_{\alpha_0}, \sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2). \quad (17)$$

Since the real and imaginary parts of $(\mathbf{H})_{i,j}$ are Gaussian distributed, the ergodic channel power $(\mathbf{H})_{i,j} (\mathbf{H})_{i,j}^*$ is given by the sum of their squared values. As a consequence, it follows a non-central chi-squared distribution with two degrees of freedom, with scaling factor $\sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2 / 2$ and non-centrality parameter $\frac{\sigma_{\alpha_0}^2}{\sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2 / 2}$ [14]. The resulting mean and variance of the Frobenius norm are

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2] = N^2 \left(\sigma_{\alpha_0}^2 + \sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2 \right), \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Var}[\|\mathbf{H}\|_F^2] = N^2 \left(\sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2 \right) \left(2\sigma_{\alpha_0}^2 + \sum_{\ell=1}^{L-1} \sigma_{\alpha_\ell}^2 \right). \quad (19)$$

Recall that each channel gain α_ℓ depends on the UAV position \mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m through D_ℓ (see Eq. (3)), which is a stochastic variable due to UAV state uncertainty. Assuming that the UAV's positional uncertainty is small relative to the UAV-ground station distance, D_ℓ can be approximated using the expected UAV position $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k+t}^m$. Indeed, for short prediction horizons T , the growth of the position covariance is limited, rendering this uncertainty negligible compared to the tens-of-meters link distance typically involved in the ergodic rate computation. Hence, substituting Eqs. (18)–(19) into Eq. (15) then yields a closed-form approximation of $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$ as a function of the control inputs, which can be used in the objective function in Eq. (11a). The ergodic rate term in Eq. (11a) is evaluated in closed form via Eqs. (15)–(19), adding negligible computation to the nonlinear optimization.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Simulation Scenario

To evaluate the proposed Communication MPC framework, a monitoring scenario typical of UAV-assisted communication and surveillance missions is considered. In this scenario, UAVs monitor a large facility while transmitting collected data to a ground station, capturing essential aspects of aerial monitoring, such as obstacle avoidance and coordinated operation in proximity to structures.

Two simulation settings are investigated. The first involves a single UAV flying near a structure, with a minimum distance $d_{\text{MIN}} = 20$ m from the monitored surface. This simplified scenario isolates the impact of accurate communication modeling, allowing direct comparison between the proposed communication-aware trajectory optimization and conventional LOS-based approaches. The UAV starts at $[-200, 225, 0]$ and aims for $\mathbf{c}^1 = [300, 225, 0]$.

To further assess the Communication MPC performance under more dynamic conditions, a second scenario with $M = 6$ UAVs in the same 3D airspace is considered. UAVs start from equidistant points on a circle of radius 200 m and aim for the diametrically opposite positions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{c}^{1:3} &= [-200, 0, 0], [-100, 100\sqrt{3}, 0], [100, 100\sqrt{3}, 0], \\ \mathbf{c}^{4:6} &= [200, 0, 0], [100, -100\sqrt{3}, 0], [-100, -100\sqrt{3}, 0]. \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the safety constraint is also designed to enforce a minimum UAV-to-obstacle and inter-UAV distance of $d_{\text{MIN}} = 20$ m, ensuring secure navigation in the confined airspace.

In both scenarios, the ground station is located at $\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} = [400, 0, -100]$, while the large structure in the environment is positioned at $y_O = 250$, extending parallel to the xz -plane. Safe operation is ensured by enforcing minimum inter-UAV and UAV-to-obstacle distance constraints with probability $1 - \epsilon = 0.99999$. The structure is assumed to be sufficiently large to generate a significant reflected propagation component between the UAVs and the ground station, resulting in $L = 2$ communication paths. Applying the mirror method to model this reflection, the (squared) distances between UAV m and the ground station for the direct and reflected paths can be computed, respectively, as

$$\begin{aligned} D_0^2 &= \sum_{j \in \{x, y, z\}} ([\mu_{j,p}]_{k+t}^m - p_{\text{BS},j})^2, \\ D_1^2 &= (2y_O - [\mu_{y,p}]_{k+t}^m - p_{\text{BS},y})^2 + \sum_{j \in \{x, z\}} ([\mu_{j,p}]_{k+t}^m - p_{\text{BS},j})^2 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $p_{\text{BS},j}$ is the j -th component of \mathbf{p}_{BS} .

The optimization problem balances flight time and communication performance using the weighting factors w_D and w_C , which normalize the relative contributions of the distance and channel rate terms in the objective

$$w_D = \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{p}_k^m - \mathbf{c}^m\|^2]}, \quad w_C = \frac{\bar{w}_C}{\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_k^m)},$$

where $\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{p}_k^m - \mathbf{c}^m\|^2]$ and $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_k^m)$ denote the expected distance-to-goal and communication ergodic rate components at the time of optimization k , respectively, and \bar{w}_C sets the trade-off between distance and communication rate.

TABLE I: Parameters used in the simulations

Carrier Frequency	$f_c = 60$ GHz
Bandwidth	$B = 1$ GHz
Transmission power	$P_{TX} = 25$ mW
Antenna size	$N = 8$
Antenna efficiency	$\eta_{\text{eff}} = 0.9$
Absolute temperature	$K_{\text{abs}} = 288.15$ K
Atmospheric pressure	101.3 kPa
Controller sampling time	$\delta T = 0.5$ s
Planning horizon	$T = 20$ steps
UAV mass	$\rho = 3$ kg
Air Resistance Attenuation Factor	$\phi = 0.9$
Model Uncertainty	$\Sigma = 0.1 \mathbf{I}_3$
Max Speed	$v_{MAX} = 14$ m/s
Max controlling force	$u_{MAX} = 10$ N
Consecutive forces deviation	$\Delta u = 2$ N

The complete set of parameters employed in the simulations is reported in Table I.

B. Ergodic Rate Approximation Validation

To validate the closed-form ergodic rate approximation presented in Eqs. (15)–(19), its values are compared against simulated results. Monte Carlo simulations were employed, sampling the 3D airspace in a grid format with 10,000 samples per location. Each simulation accounted for both channel uncertainties and UAV position uncertainties to comprehensively evaluate the approximation. To evaluate the worst-case error, UAV position uncertainties were modeled to match those associated with the predicted UAV position at the end of the planning horizon T .

The results demonstrate absolute errors below 0.04 bit/s/Hz across all sampled locations, corresponding to a maximum relative error of 0.3%. Notably, the error distribution is uniform throughout the airspace, with no regions exhibiting significantly higher errors. These findings confirm that the approximation in Eqs. (15)–(19) is highly reliable and suitable for use in the Communication MPC optimization framework. Figure 1 illustrates the values of $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$ with the introduced approximation. As further confirmation of the relevance and importance of the ergodic rate estimation introduced in Eqs. (15)–(19), Fig. 2 illustrates the relative error between the ergodic rate computed via Monte Carlo simulations and the one obtained by considering only LOS between the UAV and the ground station. Errors reach up to 35%, with significant underestimation occurring near the obstacle. As demonstrated in the next section, such discrepancies can lead to severely degraded UAV control in the airspace, potentially compromising mission objectives.

C. Impact of LOS-only vs. Multipath-aware Rate Modeling on UAV Control

To assess the influence of communication modeling on UAV trajectory planning, a single-UAV monitoring scenario was simulated under two different channel assumptions: LOS-only and the proposed multipath-aware framework. Both configurations pursued the same trade-off between mission objectives and communication performance, with a weighting factor of $\bar{w}_C = 1.75$ in the depicted example.

Results demonstrate that, when only the LOS component is assumed, the UAV approaches the ground station significantly

Fig. 1: Values of $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$ in the shared airspace (from Eqs. (15)–(19)). The airspace is discretized into ten distinct z-axis levels, each represented by a set of contours. Contour colors indicate the ergodic rate, ranging from 1 bit/s/Hz to 13 bit/s/Hz.

Fig. 2: Relative error of a LOS-only channel model with respect to the expected $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$.

more closely than in the multipath-aware assumption scenario. Specifically, the maximum distance from the monitored surface is 91.09 m under the LOS-only assumption, whereas the proposed framework yields a maximum distance of 61.32 m (see Fig. 3). This discrepancy arises from the underestimation of the true ergodic rate in the LOS-only model, which can lead to a misinformed trajectory that unnecessarily reduces the UAV-to-ground station separation. Such deviations have important operational implications. By flying closer to the ground station than necessary, the UAV may compromise its ability to maintain the optimal camera perspective for monitoring the surface. Consequently, the on-board sensor may fail to capture the necessary visual details, potentially impairing the success of the surveillance mission. These findings underscore the importance of accurate ergodic rate estimation in UAV trajectory optimization, particularly for applications that require reliable data streaming for real-time monitoring and effective control of UAVs.

D. Communication MPC Performance Evaluation

In this section, the performance of the Communication MPC optimization is evaluated in the multi-agent reference scenario by analyzing the UAVs' trajectories toward their targets and the temporal evolution of the experienced ergodic rate $\bar{R}(\mathbf{p}_{k+t}^m)$. The results are presented for two values of \bar{w}_C : (i) $\bar{w}_C = 0.5$, where the objective function in the Communication MPC optimization prioritizes speed to reach the destination, and (ii) $\bar{w}_C = 1.25$, where ergodic rate is the dominant component.

Fig. 3: Trajectories obtained by the Communication MPC when ergodic rate is modeled as in Eqs. (15)–(19) (in blue) or considering only LOS components (in red).

(a) Trajectories obtained by the Communication MPC approach, with $\bar{w}_C = 0.5$. Herein, the speed to destination dominates the objective function, with UAVs following trajectories very close to the shortest paths.

(b) Trajectories obtained by the Communication MPC approach, with $\bar{w}_C = 1.25$. Herein, the communication rate dominates, with UAVs sacrificing their speed to destination to increase the experienced ergodic rate.

Fig. 4: Trade-off between speed to destination and ergodic rate obtained with the Communication MPC approach.

Figure 4 illustrates the trajectories traveled by the UAVs. As \bar{w}_C increases, the UAVs follow longer, arched paths that bring them closer to the ground station while still reaching their target destinations. Figure 5 shows the ergodic rate experienced during flight. Overall, the proposed Communication MPC effectively balances communication performance and flight time, achieving up to a 41.7% improvement in ergodic rate when communication is prioritized, while only marginally increasing the UAVs’ flight time. Importantly, in all simulations, the distance between any pair of UAVs always remains above the minimum separation d_{MIN} .

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents a decentralized MPC framework for cooperative UAVs that jointly optimizes trajectory planning and communication performance by integrating a realistic physical-layer MIMO channel model into the control architecture. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach can effectively manage the trade-offs between mission efficiency, communication quality, and safety, enabling UAVs to adapt

Fig. 5: Ergodic rate evolution through time with $\bar{w}_C = 0.5$ (in blue) and $\bar{w}_C = 1.25$ (in red). UAVs 5 and 6 follow similar profiles as UAVs 3 and 2, respectively.

their paths according to communication priorities without compromising separation constraints or significantly increasing flight time. Future work will explore data-driven channel characterization and learning-based prediction within the control architecture, enabling the MPC to adapt to environment-specific propagation conditions. Hardware in the loop or field experiments and embedded timing benchmarks will also be considered to further assess real-time feasibility.

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